

Dear Participant

What do you think about your recent diabetes care?

We are getting in touch with you to ask for your feedback on the diabetes care you recently received from your community health care service.

Your feedback will help us find out if there are ways we can improve this service. You may choose to answer this survey or not. If you choose not to, this will not affect the diabetes care you get in any way.

Before you decide to take part in this survey, please read the information sheet enclosed which tells you more about the study.

If you would like to find out more or would like help filling out this survey please call (insert name and contact phone number)

The survey will take about 10 minutes to complete. There are no right or wrong answers, only what you think describes your experiences best.

Informed Consent to participate in a survey about your recent experiences of diabetes care with the community diabetes care team

If you are happy to take part in this survey, please read the statements below and tick each box opposite to show that you have agreed to take part in this survey and that you understand what will happen to the information you provide us. [You can then start filling out the questionnaire.](#)

1. I consent to taking part in this survey.
2. I have read and understood the information sheet for this study.
3. I have been given a contact name/phone number if I have any questions about this study.
4. I understand that taking part is voluntary and my care will not be affected if I decide not to participate.
5. I understand that the information I provide will be treated as confidential and I cannot be identified from any findings presented.
6. I agree that my anonymised data can be used for publications and meetings.
7. I understand that under the freedom of information act I can access the information I have provided if I want to.

ATTENDING THE COMMUNITY DIABETES CARE SERVICE

Part 1: You recently attended your community (insert relevant HCP e.g community diabetes nurse specialist). Thinking about your appointment with the health care professional named above, please answer the following questions:

1. **Who arranged/referred you to see this health care professional?
(please tick one box only)**

<p style="text-align: right;">GP <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p style="text-align: right;">Practice nurse <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p style="text-align: right;">Public health nurse <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p style="text-align: right;">Community diabetes nurse specialist <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p style="text-align: right;">Community dietician <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Community podiatrist <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p style="text-align: right;">Hospital outpatient diabetes clinic <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p style="text-align: right;">Don't know <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p style="text-align: right;">Other <input type="checkbox"/></p>
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If Other, please specify: _____

2. **Do you know why you were referred to see this health care professional?**

Yes

No

Not sure

3. **Is this your first appointment with this health care professional?**

Yes Go to Q4

No

If No, how many appointments have you had with this health care professional **in total**?

2 appointments

3 or more appointments

Not sure

Part 2: Thinking about your FIRST appointment with this health care professional, please answer the following questions:

4. **Was your first appointment with this health care professional:**

Within the last month Go to Q5

Over a month but less than six months ago Go to Q5
More than 6 months ago Go to Q7

5. How long did you have to wait before you had your first appointment?

Less than 2 weeks Over 8 weeks
2 – 4 weeks Can't remember
5-8 weeks

6. Do you think the health care professional had the most up to-date information about your diabetes at your first appointment?

Yes, definitely
Yes, to some extent
No
Can't remember

Part 3: Thinking about your most RECENT appointment with this health care professional, please answer the following questions: (if you have only had one appointment, then answer the questions for this first appointment)

7. How far did you have to travel to attend your most recent appointment?

Less than 5 miles
5-10 miles
More than 10 miles

8. How long were you waiting on the day of your most recent appointment before you saw the health care professional?

Less than 15 minutes
15-30 minutes
More than 30 minutes

9. Did the health care professional let you know who to contact if you had any concerns about your diabetes following your most recent appointment?

Yes
No
Can't remember

Part 4: Thinking about your appointment(s) in general with this health care professional, please answer the following questions:

10. Did you think there was enough time to discuss your diabetes care and treatments during your appointment (s)?

- Yes, definitely
Yes, to some extent
No

11. Did the health care professional ever ask you how your diabetes affects your everyday life?

- Yes, definitely
Yes, to some extent
No

12. Do you think the health care professional provided you with enough information to help you manage your diabetes?

- Not enough
Right amount
Too much

13. Were you involved as much as you wanted to be in discussions about your diabetes care and treatment?

- Yes, definitely
Yes, to some extent
No

14. Do you feel more confident about managing your diabetes after seeing this health care professional?

- Yes, definitely
Yes, somewhat
No

15. Did the health care professional provide you with any other information (for example, information leaflets, useful websites, information about diabetes education programmes) to help you manage your diabetes?

- Yes
No
Can't remember

16. Did the health care professional organise/refer you to see another

health care professional about your diabetes care?

No	<input type="checkbox"/>
Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>

If Yes, please specify who she organised/referred you to see?

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17. How was the health care professional at...
(please tick ONE box that best describes your experience)

a).. making you feel happy and relaxed ?
 (being friendly and caring and making you feel calm)

not very good	ok	good	very good	excellent	does not apply

b).. asking questions and letting you talk ?
 (being interested in you and giving you time to speak)

not very good	ok	good	very good	excellent	does not apply

c).. listening and understanding ?
 (paying attention and knowing the things you find difficult)

not very good	ok	good	very good	excellent	does not apply

d)... explaining things
 (answering questions, giving you clear information and instructions)

not very good	ok	good	very good	excellent	does not apply

e)... making a plan?

(encouraging you, talking about what to do next, involving you as much as you want)

Part 4: People with type 2 diabetes attend different health care professionals/clinics for their diabetes care. Thinking about the different health care professionals you have seen ABOUT YOUR DIABETES, please answer the following questions:

**18. Which of the following health care professionals/clinics have you attended about your diabetes in the last 12 MONTHS?
(please tick all that apply)**

- GP
- Practice Nurse
- Diabetes nurse specialist
- Dietician
- Podiatrist
- Hospital outpatient diabetes clinic
- Retinal Screen clinic
- Other (please specify)

If Other, please specify who else you have seen: _____

19. How often do you repeat information about your diabetes to different health care professionals involved in your diabetes care?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

20. How often were you confused because different health care professionals told you different things about how to manage your diabetes?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

21. Do you think the health care professionals involved in your diabetes care work together as a team to help you manage your diabetes?

- Never
- Sometimes
- Usually
- Always

Part 5: About You:

22. Are you: Male: Female:

23. What is your age?

- Under 40
- 41-55
- 56-65
- 61-70
- Over 70

24. When were you diagnosed with diabetes by a doctor/nurse?

- Less than 12 months ago
- 1-2 years ago
- 3-5 years ago
- More than 5 years ago

25. If you have any other comments please write them in the box below.

Was there anything particularly good about the diabetes care you received from this health care professional?

Was there anything that could have been improved?

Any other comments about your diabetes care?

As well as asking people to fill out this questionnaire, we would also like to speak to people to find out a bit more about their experiences of receiving diabetes care in their local community. Speaking to people with type 2 diabetes will help us plan how we can improve diabetes services. If you are happy to speak to a researcher, please give you name and contact details below:

Name: _____

Contact telephone number: _____